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DEFINING ICT IN A BOUNDARY LESS WORLD: THE DEVELOPMENT OF A WORKING HIERARCHY

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ABSTRACT

Subsequent to rapid information and communication technology development, the scope of the definition of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT or ICTs) has been utilized within diverse contexts including economic development, education, IT, business and personal usage. A review of academic literature, trade publications and general information was undertaken to establish a hierarchy of applications for the term ICT or ICTs.

KEYWORDS

ICT, ICTs, education, economics, digital communication, hierarchy

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CRITICAL SUCCESS FACTORS FOR IMPLEMENTING AN ERP SYSTEM WITHIN UNIVERSITY CONTEXT: CONCEPTS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, Information Technology (IT) plays an important role in efficiency and effectiveness of the organizational performance. As an IT application, Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems is considered one of the most important IT applications because it enables the organizations to connect and interact with its administrative units in order to manage data and organize internal procedures. Many institutions use ERP systems, most notably Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). However, many projects fail or exceed scheduling and budget constraints; the rate of failure in HEIs sector is higher than in other sectors. With HEIs' recent movement to implement ERP systems and the lack of research studies examining successful implementation in HEIs, this paper provides a critical literature review with a special focus on Saudi Arabia. Further, it defines Critical Success Factors (CSFs) contributing to the success of ERP implementation in HEIs. This paper is part of a larger research effort aiming to provide guidelines and useful findings that help HEIs to manage the challenges for ERP systems and define CSFs that will help practitioners to implement them in the Saudi context.

KEYWORDS

Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system, ERP implementation, Critical Success Factors (CSFs), Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), Higher Education

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THE ETHICAL DILEMMA OF THE USA GOVERNMENT WIRETAPPING

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ABSTRACT

USA Government wiretapping activities is a very controversial issue. Undoubtedly this technology can assist law enforced authority to detect / identify unlawful or hostile activities; however, this task raises severe privacy concerns. In this paper, we have discussed this complex information technology issue of governmental wiretapping and how it effects both public and private liberties. Legislation has had a major impact on the uses and the stigma of wiretapping for the war on terrorism. This paper also analyzes the ethical and legal concerns inherent when discussing the benefits and concerns of wiretapping. The analysis has concluded with the effects of wiretapping laws as they relate to future government actions in their fight against terrorists.

KEYWORDS

Wiretapping, government invasion of rights, terrorist attacks, eavesdropping, privacy, ethics

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AUTOMATIC RECOMMENDATION FOR ONLINE USERS USING WEB USAGE MINING

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ABSTRACT

A Real World Challenging Task Of The Web Master Of An Organization Is To Match The Needs Of User And Keep Their Attention In Their Web Site. So, Only Option Is To Capture The Intuition Of The User And Provide Them With The Recommendation List. Most Specifically, An Online Navigation Behaviour Grows With Each Passing Day, Thus Extracting Information Intelligently From It Is A Difficult Issue. Web Master Should Use Web Usage Mining Method To Capture Intuition. A Wum Is Designed To Operate On Web Server Logs Which Contain User's Navigation. Hence, Recommendation System Using Wum Can Be Used To Forecast The Navigation Pattern Of User And Recommend Those To User In A Form Of Recommendation List. In This Paper, We Propose A Two Tier Architecture For Capturing Users Intuition In The Form Of Recommendation List Containing Pages Visited By User And Pages Visited By Other User's Having Similar Usage Profile. The Practical Implementation Of Proposed Architecture And Algorithm Shows That Accuracy Of User Intuition Capturing Is Improved.

KEYWORDS

Data Mining, Web Usage mining, Web Intelligence, Personalization, Clustering, Classification

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A REVIEW OF ICT TECHNOLOGY IN CONSTRUCTION

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ABSTRACT

A growing awareness in the construction industry has emerged to pay a sharp attention to ICT as a catalyst that would mitigate the deficiencies characterized by this industry. In comparison with other cited review articles, this paper is aimed to 1) compile the research published on “ICT Technologies” in correspondence to “Construction Tasks” in the construction industry over the past two decades (1996-2016), 2) demonstrate the trends and patterns in the use of different types of ICT Technologies 3) discuss the correspondence of the identified ICT Technologies to the identified Construction Tasks and 4) exhibit the construction needs of ICT. By the employment of a five phases profiling methodology, a set of 68 out of 202 articles and papers indexed by Elsevier’s Scopus database was considered relevant for the current review paper. This research is targeting the beginning researchers and practitioners in the field of ICT in construction.

KEYWORDS

Construction industry, Information, Technology, Ict, Construction Tasks, Article review.

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PROCESSING, SWITCHING AND COMMUNICATION OF KNOWLEDGE

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ABSTRACT

The domain of knowledge¹ is more encompassing than that of wealth and materials. For dealing with utility of knowledge, all factors (its scarcity, its total utility, its marginal utility, specifically its diminishing marginal utility, its utilitarian value, its exchange value, etc.) that influence the evaluation need to be considered. From a communication perspective, knowledge can be traced backward and extrapolated forward, much like scientific parameter(s). From a structural perspective, we propose that the processing of knowledge be based on the most basic and fewest truisms. These truisms are, in turn, based on reality and they permit the characterization of information and knowledge. To this extent, computational processing does not depend on the philosophic writings of earlier economists. However, the truisms are validated from a longer-term philosophic interpretation of how these truisms have survived so that they can be expanded and reused in scientific and computational environments. This approach permits machines to process knowledge based on the content of a particular piece of information and to enhance content, the presentation and the wealth of knowledge that the information communicates.

KEYWORDS

Knowledge Representation, Knowledge Functions, Knowledge and Information Processing.

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DEVELOPING THE E-COMMERCE MODEL A CONSUMER TO CONSUMER USING BLOCKCHAIN NETWORK TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

E-commerce has increased recently because of the development of the internet and has become a new concept that is applicable to trade transaction and services providing, using information technology. This is known as e-commerce that is a means of communicating information products or services through technical tools. This research proposed model is able to take advantage of Blockchain technology to develop e-commerce especially consumer to consumer. The proposed model adds some advantages to e-commerce operations, and the possibility of developing them to reach a high percentage of profits by using blockchain technology which led to verify the information of products offered for sale. In addition, to the possibility of distributing feedback to all Blockchain users, through which it develops the mechanism of trust and cooperation between consumers, it is considered a reference point to explore the behaviour of commercial consumers which is stored in the data file of consumers. This model facilitates business processes between consumer and consumer, eliminates the central role of large business companies in controlling and setting restrictions, and to the development and expansion of this type of trade.

KEYWORDS

Blockchain, Network, E-Commerce, Consumer To Consumer.

FOR MORE DETAILS: <http://airconline.com/ijmit/V11N2/11219ijmit04.pdf>

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BARRIERS TO GOVERNMENT CLOUD ADOPTION

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ABSTRACT

Besides the benefits are there possible challenges government agencies are likely to encounter should they decide to adopt cloud computing? What strategies should be deployed to overcome the inhibitors of cloud computing? These are but few questions this paper aims to investigate. Studies have shown that, cloud computing has become a strategic direction for many government agencies and is already being deployed in many critical areas of the government's cyber infrastructure. The benefits and the challenges of cloud adoption have heightened interest of academic research in recent times. We are however uncertain, per literature factors that hinder successful cloud adoption especially in the Ghanaian context. We posit that, understanding the challenges of cloud adoption and overcoming them must accompany the use of the technology in order to prevent unwanted technical consequences, and even greater problems from government information management. This study is based on unstructured interviews from selected government agencies in Ghana. The study is grounded on the theory of technology, organization and environment (TOE) framework. Major inhibiting factors identified include lack of basic infrastructure for cloud take-off, data security, unreliable internet connectivity, and general lack of institutional readiness

KEYWORDS

Cloud-computing, adoption, challenges, deployment-models, virtualization.

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SIMULATING HYPE CYCLE CURVES WITH MATHEMATICAL FUNCTIONS: SOME EXAMPLES OF HIGH-TECH TRENDS IN JAPAN

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a method to simulate Gartner's hype cycle [1] is proposed. A search of the academic literature on this topic provides no clear guidance on how to draw hype cycle curves with mathematical functions. This article explores a new process for simulating the curve as a combination of bell-shaped curves and S-shaped curves, and applies this process to some high-tech innovations in Japan. Trends in technologies such as customer relationship management (CRM), supply chain management (SCM), and cloud computing are analyzed by using a corpus of 4,772 newspaper articles. For these examples, Gompertz functions show better fit than logistic functions. For the combined curve, polynomial functions of degree 9 provide the best fit, with adjusted R-square values of more than 0.97.

KEYWORDS

Hype cycle, High-tech innovation, S-shaped curves, Diffusion of innovations

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THE CONTRIBUTION OF ELECTRONIC BANKING TO CUSTOMER SATISFACTION: A CASE OF GCB BANK LIMITED –KOFORIDUA

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ABSTRACT

Internet banking has the potential to provide fast and reliable services to customers for which they are relatively happy. Due to the technological changes taking place all over the world, many institutions, including the banking sector have taken giant steps to move in tandem with these changes. In this light most banks, with GCB Bank, Ghana, not being an exception have introduced electronic banking in order to decongest the banking halls of customers who spend time unending in order to transact business. The purpose of this research was to assess the Contribution of Electronic Banking to Customer Satisfaction at GCB Bank-Koforidua, to this end some objectives were set for the study. These were: To assess the availability of electronic banking facilities at GCB Bank, Koforidua. To assess the knowledge and patronage of internet banking services by customers, to examine the effectiveness of the usage of electronic banking facilities, to examine the problem facing an internet banking in GCB Bank, Koforidua. This is a quantitative study that employed the use of questionnaires as the main tools for data collection. Data was collected from management, staff and customers of GCB Bank, Koforidua Branch. Findings from analysis of data revealed that though there was the existence of internet banking facilities of the bank, respondents of the study were not fully aware of the existence of such facilities. It was also found that the use of internet banking was quite expensive and that though the bank was utilizing the facility, customers were not fully patronizing them. It was concluded that internet banking brings efficiency in the operations of the bank. Finally, the study recommended that all branches of GCB Bank adopt internet banking facilities to help in effective banking operations and transactional purposes. To maximize the operations and potential of the bank management must endeavor to educate the customers about the existence of internet banking facilities since a few customers were aware of the existence of such facilities.

KEYWORDS

internet banking, customer satisfaction, contribution, Ghana, ATM Cards, master cards, visa, debit & credit cards

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